

Table S2. List of studied fly species with their host plants and GenBank/DBJ accession numbers for five genes.

Sample No.	Family	Fly species	Source	Host plant phylum	Host plant species	GenBank/DBJ accession number				
						28S	CO1	16S	18S	CAD
1	Agromyzidae	<i>Agromyza ambrosivora</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104822	EF104649	-	-	EF104735
2	Agromyzidae	<i>Agromyza frontella</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104823	EF104650	-	-	EF104736
3	Agromyzidae	<i>Hexomyza schineri</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104827	EF104654	-	-	EF104740
4	Agromyzidae	<i>Japanagromyza viridula</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104828	EF104655	-	-	-
5	Agromyzidae	<i>Melanagromyza minimoides</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104831	EF104658	-	-	EF104743
6	Agromyzidae	<i>Melanagromyza obtusa</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104832	EF104659	-	-	EF104744
7	Agromyzidae	<i>Ophiomyia nasuta</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104834	EF104661	-	-	EF104746
8	Agromyzidae	<i>Ophiomyia lantanae</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104836	EF104663	-	-	EF104748
9	Agromyzidae	<i>Tropicomys theae</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104841	EF104668	-	-	EF104753
10	Agromyzidae	<i>Amauromyza flavifrons</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104842	EF104669	-	-	EF104754
11	Agromyzidae	<i>Amauromyza monofalconensis</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104843	EF104670	-	-	EF104755
12	Agromyzidae	<i>Aulagromyza discrepans</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104845	EF104672	-	-	EF104757
13	Agromyzidae	<i>Aulagromyza luteoscutellata</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104846	EF104673	-	-	EF104758
14	Agromyzidae	<i>Aulagromyza nitida</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104847	EF104674	-	-	EF104759
15	Agromyzidae	<i>Aulagromyza orbitalis</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104848	EF104675	-	-	EF104760
16	Agromyzidae	<i>Aulagromyza tridentate</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104849	EF104676	-	-	EF104761
17	Agromyzidae	<i>Calycomyza hyptidis</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104851	EF104678	-	-	EF104763
18	Agromyzidae	<i>Calycomyza malvae</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104854	EF104681	-	-	EF104766
19	Agromyzidae	<i>Cerodontha B angulata</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104856	EF104683	-	-	EF104768
20	Agromyzidae	<i>Cerodontha X atronitens</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104857	EF104684	-	-	EF104769
21	Agromyzidae	<i>Chromatomyia lactucae</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104866	EF104693	-	-	EF104778
22	Agromyzidae	<i>Galiomyza violivora</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104870	EF104697	-	-	EF104782
23	Agromyzidae	<i>Gynophytomyza heteroneura</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104871	EF104698	-	-	EF104783
24	Agromyzidae	<i>Liriomyza philadelphivora</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104877	EF104704	-	-	EF104789
25	Agromyzidae	<i>Liriomyza trifolii</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104879	DQ516575	-	-	EF104791
26	Agromyzidae	<i>Metopomyza scutellata</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104880	EF104706	-	-	EF104792
27	Agromyzidae	<i>Metopomyza flavonotata</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104881	EF104707	-	-	EF104793
28	Agromyzidae	<i>Napomyza cichorii</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104882	EF104708	-	-	EF104794
29	Agromyzidae	<i>Napomyza montanoides</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104885	EF104711	-	-	EF104797
30	Agromyzidae	<i>Nemorimyza posticata</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104888	EF104714	-	-	EF104800
31	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytobia betulae</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104890	EF104716	-	-	EF104802
32	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytobia setosa</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104891	EF104717	-	-	EF104803
33	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza arctica</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104893	EF104719	-	-	EF104805
34	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza felti</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (fern)		EF104894	EF104720	-	-	EF104806
35	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza melampyga</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104895	EF104721	-	-	EF104807
36	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza robiniae</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104896	EF104722	-	-	EF104808
37	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytomyza aquilegiana</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104898	EF104724	-	-	EF104810
38	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytomyza evanescens</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104904	EF104730	-	-	EF104816
39	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytomyza ilicicola</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104902	EF104728	-	-	EF104814
40	Agromyzidae	<i>Pseudonapomyza lacteipennis</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		EF104906	EF104732	-	-	EF104818
42	Asteiidae	<i>Asteia amoena</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		GU299218	MG120612	-	-	GU299255
43	Tephritidae	<i>Campiglossa pygmaea</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		HM062625	HM062547	-	-	-
44	Clusiidae	<i>Clusia czernyi</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		FJ890873	FJ435903	-	-	GU299263
45	Clusiidae	<i>Clusiodes johnsoni</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		FJ890856	FJ435912	-	-	GU299264
46	Fergusoninidae	<i>Fergusonina turneri</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		KC177790	KY378336	-	-	KY378132
47	Opomyzidae	<i>Geomyza tripunctata</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		GU299222	HM412176	-	-	-
48	Oдиниidae	<i>Odimia boletina</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		-	MZ623216	-	-	GU299272
49	Opomyzidae	<i>Opomyza florum</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		KC177795	MZ628313	KJ418480	-	-

50	Ephydridae	<i>Psilopa polita</i>	GenBank	tracheophyte (angiosperm)		KC177805	MZ626101	-	-	-
a20	Agromyzidae	<i>Chromatomyia</i> sp.	this study	tracheophyte (fern)	<i>Asplenium varians</i>	LC743998	LC743999	-	-	-
a92	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza luna</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum salebrosum</i>	LC707313	LC707543	LC707266	LC707591	LC707639
a99	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza ugetsu</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum orientalis</i>	LC707314	LC707544	LC707267	LC707592	LC707640
a101	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza caliginosa</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum purpureorubrum</i>	LC707315	LC707545	LC707268	LC707593	LC707641
a108	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza izayoi</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum orientalis</i>	LC707316	LC707546	LC707269	LC707594	LC707642
a146	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza nigroflava</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum salebrosum</i>	LC707317	LC707547	LC707270	LC707595	LC707643
a156	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza luteola</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum purpureorubrum</i>	LC707318	LC707548	LC707271	LC707596	LC707644
a166	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza chichibuensis</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum purpureorubrum</i>	LC707319	LC707549	LC707272	LC707597	LC707645
a167	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza helva</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum purpureorubrum</i>	LC707320	LC707550	LC707273	LC707598	LC707646
a169	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza pallidofasciata</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum purpureorubrum</i>	LC707321	LC707551	LC707274	LC707599	LC707647
a191	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza brunofasciata</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum salebrosum</i>	LC707322	LC707552	LC707275	LC707600	LC707648
a193	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza bifasciata</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum orientalis</i>	LC707323	LC707553	LC707276	LC707601	LC707649
a201	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza lanternaria</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum salebrosum</i>	LC707324	LC707554	LC707277	LC707602	LC707650
a202	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza alpicola</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum purpureorubrum</i>	LC707325	LC707555	LC707278	LC707603	LC707651
a204	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza tsukuyomi</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Marchantia polymorpha</i>	LC707326	LC707556	LC707279	LC707604	LC707652
a215	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza conocephali</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Conocephalum orientalis</i>	LC707327	LC707557	LC707280	LC707605	LC707653
a220	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza comettiformis</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Reboulia hemisphaerica orientalis</i>	LC707328	LC707558	LC707281	LC707606	LC707654
a228	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza falcata</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Reboulia hemisphaerica orientalis</i>	LC707329	LC707559	LC707282	LC707607	LC707655
a236	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza aratriformis</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Reboulia hemisphaerica orientalis</i>	LC707330	LC707560	LC707283	LC707608	LC707656
a237	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza rebouliae</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Reboulia hemisphaerica orientalis</i>	LC707331	LC707561	LC707284	LC707609	-
a242	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza argentifasciata</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Reboulia hemisphaerica orientalis</i>	LC707332	LC707562	LC707285	LC707610	LC707657
a243	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza longifurcae</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Plagiochasma pterospermum</i>	LC707333	LC707563	LC707286	LC707611	LC707658
a251	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza plagiochasmato</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Plagiochasma pterospermum</i>	LC707334	LC707564	LC707287	LC707612	LC707659
a262	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza calcicola</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Plagiochasma pterospermum</i>	LC707335	LC707565	LC707288	LC707613	LC707660
a264	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza arcus</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Plagiochasma pterospermum</i>	LC707336	LC707566	LC707289	LC707614	LC707661
a271	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza dumortierae</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Dumortiera hirsuta</i>	LC707337	LC707567	LC707290	LC707615	LC707662
a277	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza crepusculum</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Dumortiera hirsuta</i>	LC707338	LC707568	LC707291	LC707616	-
a283	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza wiesnerellae</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Wiesnerella denudata</i>	LC707339	LC707569	LC707292	LC707617	LC707663
a286	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza iriomotensis</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Asterella liukiensis</i>	LC707354	LC707584	-	LC707632	LC707674
a293	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza igniculus</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Marchantia polymorpha</i>	LC707340	LC707570	LC707293	LC707618	LC707664
a318	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza marchantiae</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Marchantia paleacea diptera</i>	LC707341	LC707571	LC707294	LC707619	LC707665
a333	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza nubatama</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Marchantia papillata grossibarba</i>	LC707342	LC707572	LC707295	LC707620	LC707666
a336	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza ricciae</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Riccia huebeneriana</i>	LC707355	LC707585	LC707307	LC707633	-
a337	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza caerulescens</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Riccia billardieri</i>	LC707356	LC707586	LC707308	LC707634	-
a339	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza sexfasciata</i>	this study	bryophyte (liverwort)	<i>Riccia lamellosa</i>	LC707358	LC707588	LC707310	LC707636	-
a341	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza foliocerotis</i>	this study	bryophyte (hornwort)	<i>Folioceros fuciformis</i>	LC707343	LC707573	LC707296	LC707621	LC707667
a342	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza megacerotis</i>	this study	bryophyte (hornwort)	<i>Megaceros flagellaris</i>	LC707344	LC707574	LC707297	LC707622	LC707668
a344	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza phaeocerotis</i>	this study	bryophyte (hornwort)	<i>Phaeoceros carolinianus</i>	LC707360	LC707590	LC707312	LC707638	LC707675
a346	Agromyzidae	<i>Chromatomyia masumiae</i>	this study	tracheophyte (fern)	<i>Lepisorus thunbergianus</i>	LC707345	LC707575	LC707298	LC707623	LC707669
a350	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytomyza suikazurae</i>	this study	tracheophyte (angiosperm)	<i>Lonicera japonica</i>	LC707346	LC707576	LC707299	LC707624	LC707670
a351	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytomyza</i> sp.	this study	tracheophyte (angiosperm)	<i>Lonicera maccckii</i>	LC707347	LC707577	LC707300	LC707625	-
a353	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytomyza</i> aff. <i>abeliae</i>	this study	tracheophyte (angiosperm)	<i>Abelia spathulata</i>	LC707348	LC707578	LC707301	LC707626	LC707671
a355	Agromyzidae	<i>Phytoliriomyza</i> aff. <i>melampyga</i>	this study	tracheophyte (angiosperm)	<i>Impatiens textorii</i>	LC707349	LC707579	LC707302	LC707627	LC707672
a356	Agromyzidae	<i>Liriomyza asterivora</i>	this study	tracheophyte (angiosperm)	<i>Aster microcephalus</i>	LC707350	LC707580	LC707303	LC707628	LC707673
a357	Agromyzidae	<i>Liriomyza takakoe</i>	this study	tracheophyte (angiosperm)	<i>Viola hondoensis</i>	LC707351	LC707581	LC707304	LC707629	-
a358	Agromyzidae	<i>Liriomyza</i> aff. <i>trifolii</i>	this study	tracheophyte (angiosperm)	<i>Vicia cracca</i>	LC707352	LC707582	LC707305	LC707630	-
a359	Agromyzidae	<i>Ophiomyza</i> sp.	this study	tracheophyte (angiosperm)	<i>Ophiorrhiza japonica</i>	LC707353	LC707583	LC707306	LC707631	-